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BASIC TECHNOLOGY OF CONSTRUCTION OF LARGE PANEL BUILDINGS

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Abstract. *In the article, buildings made of large blocks and panels, their types and structural schemes, constructions in places with special geophysical conditions, earthquake resistance of buildings. The characteristics of dimensional planning and constructive solutions are explained.*

Keywords: *building, panels, constructions, geophysical conditions, structural.*

Buildings built from small elements do not allow mechanization and automation in construction. One of the main ways of industrialization of construction production at a high level is to design and build a building from large blocks. Comparing the technical and economic indicators of buildings made of large blocks and bricks shows that the construction of a large block building takes 15% less time and 20% less labor.

Buildings made of solid or hollow large stones whose walls weigh from 0.3 tons to 3.0 tons are called large block buildings. In such buildings, all structural elements consist of large elements. Blocks are made of lightweight concrete (keramsite concrete, slag concrete, aerated concrete) and local materials (chiganoktosh, stone). Large blocks are also worn from fingers. The shape of the blocks consists mainly of rectangular parallelepipeds.

This structural scheme with internal and external retaining walls is considered the optimal option for large-block buildings. In such a scheme, reinforced concrete beams of the same size are supported on the inner and outer walls. When these vents are installed, they also act as a horizontal diaphragm. External wall blocks, in turn, act as load-bearing and impact structures. Their thickness is determined by thermotechnical calculations, taking into account the climatic conditions.

In construction, large-block buildings can be divided into two-row and four-row types according to their seams. The picture below shows the main types of blocks used in residential buildings. On the side edges of the blocks used between the windows, there are grooves, and on the blocks under the window there are slots.

Paving blocks have notches that go up (to support the intermediate plates) and down (to accommodate the window frames). If there is no window in the walls, in the round part of the building, the thickness of the balustrade blocks is 100 mm less than the thickness of the burning blocks between the windows, and it is planned to install central heating system batteries in this place. In addition to these, there are special types of large blocks, namely corner block, tsokolbop, bugotbop, stair wall blocks and sanitary-technical blocks. In order to reduce the weight of the blocks used for the outer walls, they are lined with two cylindrical bushings. The type of large blocks used for double-row walls, for residential buildings with a floor height of 2.8 m, which are burned at the window sills, have a height of 2180 mm, a width of 990, 1190, 1890, 1590 and 1790 mm.

The height of the block used for paving is 580 mm, the width is 1980, 2380, 2780 and 3180 mm. The height of the block under the window is 840 mm and the width is 990, 1190, 1790, 1990 mm. The holes inside the blocks (thickness 300 mm) used for internal walls are cylindrical or round and serve as ventilation shafts. They are 2180 mm high, 1190, 1590 and 2390 mm wide. The internal and external surfaces of all types of blocks are finished. The blocks are installed one above the other and a 10-20 mm thick mixture is laid between them. Great attention is paid to the tightness of the seams. Vertical seams can be of two types - open or closed. Open seams are located in the vertical seams where the blocks used in the walls between the windows and doors are joined. Closed seams are formed between the inner wall blocks and the horizontal corners of the outer wall, and the outer window block and the blocks between the windows are included in the adjacent seams. On both sides, hemp ropes are sewn to the vertical seams, and they are filled with a 20-30 mm deep mixture.

The horizontal seams of the rovok block and the belt blocks are welded to the hooks of the conveyors or zaklad straps or the details of the zaklad at each floor height. Apart from these, the reinforcements removed from the ends of the intermediate plates are welded with blocks, and the integrity of the building is increased.

Flat steel reinforcements are welded to the zaklad detail in order to firmly connect the daily and the hinged walls to each other. In order to prevent the formation of cracks in the adjacent part of the daily and hinged walls, reinforced concrete "keys" are burned in these places, which accept external loads from the anchors.

Special corner fasteners made of flat, round steel rods are installed over the external corners where the rovok and belt blocks are connected.

Tsokolbop blocks are installed on the leveling layer, that is, the waterproofing layer, which is spread over the foundation. Bugot blocks, anchors, are attached to the attic insulation panel. When installing balconies and verandas, plates are placed in slots raised in blocks.

Constructions in places with special geophysical conditions. Construction in places with special geophysical conditions means constructions that take into account additional effects that lead to their destruction and deterioration of sanitary and hygienic conditions during the design, construction and operation of buildings. One of the main such additional effects is the effect of an earthquake resulting from an earthquake.

An earthquake is an elastic shaking of the earth's surface as a result of the tectonic processes that occur as a result of the sliding of rocks in the deep layers of the earth against each other. Earthquake strength is measured in points. (GOST 6249-52). Buildings and structures are not damaged when the earthquake strength is up to 6 points. In such cases, separate cracks are formed on the two wall surfaces of the building structures, and mainly the facade of the building can be damaged.

When the strength of the earthquake is 6 points, it is considered strong, and it can lead to collapse of buildings and non-dangerous cracks in the supporting structures. Earthquakes with a magnitude of 7 or more are considered dangerous. In this case, the bridges may be damaged, buildings may be destroyed, and some parts of them may collapse.

As a result of the earthquake, the rocks in the earth's crust are broken and large deformations occur in them. The limited area in the earth's crust where the displacement process begins is called the "hypocenter" (or focus) of the earthquake. The projection of the focus on the surface of the earth is called "epicenter". The distance from the epicenter to any point on the earth's surface is called the epicentral distance. Vertical constituents in epicentral zones exceed horizontal constituents and decrease with distance from the epicenter. In this case, the horizontal component is the main one, which is considered dangerous for buildings and structures. Buildings and structures built in earthquake-prone regions have separate requirements for earthquake resistance. In the design, the level of earthquake is determined using the standard or earthquake map, and the earthquake tolerance value of the building is determined using SNiP P-7-81 "Construction in earthquake regions".

Several measures are used to increase the earthquake resistance of brick-walled buildings. In this case, the stability and spatial integrity of the building is provided by the cast or precast reinforced concrete belt arch, which is installed horizontally and vertically over the walls in the plane of the inter-floor covering and roof covering. Cast reinforced concrete reinforcement must be continuous. Reinforcements of these belts, in turn, are interconnected with the help of steel reinforcements of reinforced concrete columns, which form a spatial framework.

If the reinforced concrete interlayer is installed along the contour of the wall of the building, it will be possible if the belts against the earthquake are not burned in its plane.

The anti-earthquake belt should be installed along the entire width of the wall and its height should be at least 150 mm. If the wall thickness is 500 mm or more, the belt width can be taken 100-150 mm smaller than the wall width. On the other hand, the height of brick building walls for each floor should not exceed 5, 4 and 3.5 m respectively in regions with earthquake strength 7, 8 and 9. If the walls are strengthened by inserting reinforced concrete into them, the height of the floor can be increased to 6.5 and 4.5 m according to the above earthquake force.

Earthquake resistance of buildings. Volumetric planning and characteristics of structural solutions

Resistance of buildings and structures to earthquakes is called earthquake resistance. In order to ensure sufficient earthquake resistance of the buildings in the regions where the earth moves, it is necessary to take into account that these structures are also affected by horizontal forces during an earthquake in addition to the forces of gravity. These forces have a recurring nature and can act in different directions.

In order to simplify the calculations, the construction norms recommend to calculate only horizontal seismic forces directed along the lines of symmetry corresponding to the largest and the smallest height of the building.

During the construction of residential buildings inhabited by the population in the areas of land erosion, it is necessary to remove the bridged compacted zones and large bush areas between the buildings. This event is mainly considered an event against engine, preventing the spread of engine. In addition, according to the norm, the width of the building and the distance between the buildings are taken to be 15-20% larger.

When developing a project of a building and structure, it is necessary to follow the basic rules of the country. Size-planning and structural solutions should meet the conditions of symmetry and equal distribution of mass and uniformity.

If the task of the building and the requirements of the architectural planning require the building to be built in a symmetrical and complex form, then the building plan is divided into blocks with anti-seismic seams. These seams are also used to divide the building plans into sections, the dimensions of which are larger than the norm.

In buildings with retaining walls, anti-seismic joints are installed with a thick wall, and in concrete buildings.

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